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The Tourism Potential of the Jizzakh Region is becoming the Main Driver Sector of the Economy

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Our country has tremendous potential in the field of Tourism. For this reason, special attention is paid to the consistent development of tourism, improving the quality of the types of services provided, increasing the flow of tourists coming to our country. For example, the visa regime was simplified, new tourist routes were established, infrastructure was improving, the tourist image of the country was created. As a result, the number of tourists and the income from them increases from year to year. We can also see this on the example of the Jizzakh region alone.

Jizzakh is one of the few regions in our republic with a mountain, a park, a lake, a desert. The favorable geographical location of the Oasis, its beautiful nature, architectural monuments, national folk games, traditions, food captivate not only domestic, foreign tourists.

Also, the Forish district attracts the attention of tourists its unique nature, high mountains, blue lakes, fauna and rural lifestyle. The visit of foreign tourists is increasing for the sake of the ancient village Khayat, Customs and National Handicrafts, preserved in the Forish district, and the beautiful view of the wild.

Special attention is paid to the development of tourism in Jizzakh region. There are state reserves and national parks in Zaamin and Forish districts, as well as unique species of flora and fauna in the waters of Aydar-Arnasay lakes. The centuries-old customs and traditions of our people, folk dances are developing as masterpieces of our national culture.

Today, the Forish district is visited by foreign tourists from England, Russia, Italia, France, Germany and other countries. Resorts and a hotel, family guest houses are being established for these tourists

The natural climate and ecological situation of Forish district, mountains and steppes, Aydarkol, Okhum, Porasht, Kattabagdon, Yomchi and mountainous regions allow us to develop ecotourism. This sector of tourism is beneficial due to its low cost, which helps to improve the socio-economic situation of our remote villages. The main purpose of ecotourism is to communicate directly with all aspects of nature, to remind people who are tired of factory smoke, polluted air, water and noise, and social conflicts, the beauty of life. There are two hotels in the village of Porasht - OldForish, which is very suitable for ecotourism. One of the main conditions of ecotourism is the nature of the area, the lack of significant changes in the overall appearance, that is, the construction of separate buildings for luxury hotels, restaurants and other services.

It is tourists who visit the family guest houses, hostels in the National urf in the village of Yumumva Asraf of the Forish district and travel to the Wiccan mountains and Wild Fauna. Tourism services for tourists in this village are engaged in the processes of horseback riding, preparation of national dishes and get acquainted with the activities of artisans.

Foreign tourists are visiting the “Hayat” hostel and the family guest house “Yozigul” in the village of Uxum, studying the customs of this village and hiking its beautiful nature. Jizzakh is also an important factor in the development of tourism in the region, in turn, the rise of our economy, the increase in foreign exchange revenues, the creation of new jobs, the improvement of income and living standards of the population.

Another important factor is the development of tourism in the Jizzakh region, along with the economic stimulation of developing, the availability of money transfers, the presence of , the settlement of inbound and life style.